

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA 8	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 63.3884 Max: 63.5718	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1306 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	 Gabu Project
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In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Photos: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 1328-1331	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:
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DEFINITION rubble layer along bedrock	Covered by <input type="checkbox"/> SU: 1306	Fills 1489-1490 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1322	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX clay 5% silt 60% sand 35%
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery M <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles M <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Amphorae M <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) R <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Glass R	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) F <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Travertine R <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones F <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth M <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Shells R <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	Compaction <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft
			Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Depth: Original Not Original

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to: 1279	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by: 1280	Abuts:
Is covered by:	Covers:
Is cut by: 1209	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills: 1322

OBSERVATIONS
 Documentation begun in 2010, Not Excavated, Fully excavated in 2011.
 NB. - Originally shot in in 2010 - RESHOT in 2011
 Δ981: Black Glass Miniature
 Δ982: small vessel
 Δ982: Bronze "Bell"

DESCRIPTION
 Position within sector: at the northeastern edge of 2010 Trench B
 Shape: long, roughly rectangular

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): no slope; visible are stones and travertine fragments and a few fragments of ceramica commune

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): even distribution of larger tufo fragments
 Animal bones cluster to the west

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): thickness constant

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commigled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:

Cut edges: rounded straight

Cut sides: straight concave convex sloping

Cut bottom: flat concave irregular

How is cut top edge? sharp rounded

How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded

Observations:

1157 (?)
1209
1306
1322

PRELIMINARY SKETCH (2010)
 SEE BACK FOR 2011 SKETCH

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

loose fill adjacent to bedrock, most likely still part of the big robbing trench 1209. Fully delimited & excavated in 2011 → 1306 appears to represent the fill of a Foundation trench built for the construction of the northern walls of our courtyard building. The trench also served as the cut for a terrace in the belvedere, which is at a higher elevation to the north. Finds appear very similar to those in SU 1279, which may represent the same fill as the trench curves around the eastern side of the structure. Western limit is arbitrary & this rubble fill appears to continue in that direction as well.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	CMM	on	02.08.2010
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